

The following section presents the textual descriptions of each interviewee for each research question.

RQ1. What was the trajectory followed to become a leader?

Megan: Megan initially did not intend to become a leader. However, during one of the meetings she attended, she reported that a more complex project emerged—one that no one else wanted to take on due to the difficulty of the area. Megan chose to accept the challenge and proposed a solution. In this way, her interest in the challenge led her to create an opportunity for her career, ultimately resulting in her first management position. The participant stated: *“Things don’t always come easily in life, like someone saying, ‘Megan, do you want to take on that position, with that team?’ For me, it didn’t happen that way. If I wanted it, I had to create the opportunity”*.

Grace: For Grace, the path to leadership was a natural process and, despite not seeking leadership, her work was consistently recognized. In this recognition, the participant mentioned that certain characteristics drew the attention of managers, who in turn offered more opportunities. Among these characteristics are accumulated experience and knowledge, whether gained over time or through a personal desire to learn more. This desire, combined with her ability to “do things differently”, that is, the distinct decisions she made throughout her projects helped Grace attain leadership positions. Her drive to learn and the broad perspective she developed enabled her to consistently take on responsibilities beyond the scope of her formal role. According to the participant: *“I was never chasing the position; it was always about the recognition of my work, my stance, and how I approach projects. That’s what opened up opportunities for me.”*

Lamarr: Lamarr understands her trajectory to leadership as a natural process. Initially, she did not aspire to be a leader; however, the experience and knowledge she acquired in the field enabled her transition into these roles. In addition, the participant highlighted her skill and enjoyment in working with people, which was also recognized by other managers. As a result of this ability, she was invited to apply for a management position. According to Lamarr: *“What led me to the path of leadership was my experience and the fact that I enjoy dealing with people”*.

Susan: Susan, the fourth participant, took part in the structuring process of one of the companies where she worked, which allowed her to identify growth opportunities. In this sense, leadership emerged as an opportunity resulting from the combination of her aspirations, the opportunity itself, and the role she played in building the area in which she worked. The participant stated: *“So it was very much a matter of building things, very much about the opportunity of the moment aligned with what I was seeking.”* Additionally, certain skills also supported Susan’s trajectory. She commented that she has always enjoyed working with people and has consistently sought professional growth, that is, she pursued higher positions and new opportunities, especially when she perceived that her current area had become stable. Two other practices that contributed to her achieving leadership roles were actively seeking feedback to understand her context and observing others’ management styles, which helped her identify what to do differently and how to improve. According to Susan: *“I was always asking for feedback, gathering insights... When I wasn’t*

in a managerial role, I tried to understand what I could do differently if I were. Those were always the things that guided me in trying to be better”.

Marissa: The final participant, Marissa, understands her trajectory as a natural process. Although she never intended to lead, she recognized in herself a natural ability for management and understood that this ability was also recognized by others, as she was invited to all the management positions she held, that is, opportunities were consistently offered to her. In addition, Marissa also recognizes her ability to work with people. According to her: *“I think I have a natural ability for management, for dealing with people and building connections”.*

RQ2. What are the main challenges faced throughout the trajectory?

Megan: Megan identifies motherhood as one of her main challenges, as she believes that most mothers tend to be more concerned with their children than fathers. As a consequence of motherhood, Megan also reports facing the challenge of the double workload. She stated: *“...it’s not easy, you know? As much as we want to think differently, the burden on women at home is still greater... If I take on all the responsibilities of the house, the children, school, and work, it just doesn’t work. The double, triple, quadruple workload exists, it really does.”* She also commented on the fact that the technology field is predominantly male and, in her view, women should not feel inferior because of their gender, but rather strive to stay one step ahead. As she put it: *“When you already take a step back and think, ‘Oh, he won’t listen to me, so-and-so won’t listen to me. That meeting is all men, and no one will listen to me because I’m a woman,’ you already start owing something. So, as women, we have to start one step ahead.”* Due to the strong male presence, Megan also experienced behavioral changes from her team because of her gender, as she was the only woman present changes that can be understood as manifestations of gender prejudice.

Grace: Grace also mentioned motherhood as a challenge, particularly during her pregnancy, which occurred at a time of career transition, making it more difficult to reconcile responsibilities, such as when she could not attend her daughters’ school events due to work. In this sense, the double workload was also a challenge, though not perceived as heavy or negative, as illustrated in her statement: *“So even when I got home and on weekends, I had to dedicate myself to the house, my daughters, and my husband... I never saw this as a burden in a negative way. I always did it because I wanted to.”*

Although she did not explicitly name it as a challenge, Grace perceives the technology field as predominantly male, noting that in one team she was the only woman among 180 people. She experienced gender prejudice in one of the teams she led, as she was the only woman among five male leaders, one of whom displayed sexist behavior, particularly because he believed he deserved the position she held. In addition to gender prejudice, Grace also experienced physical and behavioral prejudice. She believes that her East Asian background combined with being a woman may have triggered stereotypes, as she noted: *“People associate being Asian with submissiveness, so I had to be careful that this stereotype wouldn’t be interpreted as my position as a leader.”* This possibility generated internal insecurity. Grace also faced prejudice related to gender and age. Being young and a woman in a leadership role, people questioned her position and competence and associated her

appearance with limited knowledge. In one team she led, other leaders attempted to mislead her about the progress of a project because they assumed she would not understand the details or would not seek clarification. According to Grace: *"They treated me like I was a baby... That's why I say appearance leads to assumptions, right? You associate appearance with certain kinds of knowledge. At least that's what I experienced."* As a result of these prejudices, she felt a constant need to prove her competence in her daily work.

Grace also faced insecurities with each new position, as she often encountered professionals with more experience than herself. She reported self-criticism, questioning her passive stance in the face of so many opportunities. More delicately, she also experienced covert sexual harassment. One of her managers viewed all women as potential romantic prospects, as she shared: *"I joined a team where the manager was kind of, maybe that word is strong, but he was kind of sleazy. For him, every woman was a potential target to approach, you know, to have something. I had to deal with that at the time... Without meaning to, I ended up seeing a conversation between him and his two right-hand men."* Another challenge was moral suspicion, as some people doubted how she obtained one of her leadership roles, hearing comments that she was the "director's protégée." From a technical standpoint, she also mentioned the challenge of identifying the best solution for a project by evaluating different experiences shared by other professionals to determine which was most appropriate.

Lamarr: The third participant, Lamarr, also views motherhood as one of the challenges she faced throughout her trajectory. In her view, mothers tend to be much more detail-oriented regarding their children, which adds to their responsibilities. She believes it is intrinsic for women to pay attention to more aspects related to their children, which can interfere with daily work. As a result of motherhood and domestic responsibilities, Lamarr believes her professional development could have been greater if she had more time to focus on work or further studies. In addition, the career pause during maternity leave contributed to a feeling of lagging behind, and she believes her development would have been faster had she not taken that break. She commented: *"Maybe I would have developed faster if I hadn't stopped, yes, but those are life choices you make, right? It wasn't even the company holding me back; they always gave me opportunities. But of course, I stopped for five months. I stopped. Obviously, that has some impact."* In this sense, balancing personal and professional life—that is, managing the double workload was another challenge she faced.

Lamarr also experienced gender prejudice, particularly from women toward other women, noticing greater criticism coming from them. She shared: *"A woman complaining about another woman is funny. 'Oh, so-and-so only talks about her kids.' And it adds nothing good to the work, nothing that helps me. I felt that, but it came from women themselves. Women are sometimes critical of other women, it's not even about men."* From a more internal perspective, she also expressed fear about becoming a leader, as illustrated by this excerpt: *"When I became a manager for the first time, I was scared. I remember telling the HR manager, 'Is there a course for managers? Because I need one.'" She also mentioned feelings of inferiority at certain moments, recognizing them as impostor syndrome. Seeing many peer managers still actively programming, she sometimes felt out of place in meetings, as she stated: "All the time I thought, 'My God, they're going to realize that I'm the least capable person to manage this team. I have no conditions at all.'" Finally, from a technical*

perspective, Lamarr noted that the more involved she became in management, the harder it was to keep up with new technologies and techniques.

Susan: Susan, the fourth participant, mentioned motherhood as a challenge, especially because her pregnancy occurred during the 2019 pandemic. Returning from maternity leave required learning to cope with the feeling of leaving people without support. As she had always prioritized work in her career, becoming a mother required her to understand and manage the “before” and “after” of motherhood, learning not to blame herself for personal events that could affect work, as well as for the new responsibilities that emerged. Shortly after her pregnancy, she already expressed concern about work progress and her team, which intensified the double workload and required better organization to balance professional life and family responsibilities.

Gender, physical, and behavioral prejudice was another challenge she faced. Her physical characteristics and more introverted demeanor were cited by others as factors that influenced how she was perceived—seen as insecure and lacking credibility—which affected her psychologically. She reported: *“Sometimes I had to hear that I was too frail, that I didn’t convey much confidence because of my body type, that I’m smaller, right? And that sometimes didn’t convey credibility, or that I’m more of a listener than a speaker, a matter of being shy. These were things that were sometimes hard to hear, sometimes necessary but maybe at that point I wasn’t fully prepared to hear them.”* Regarding being a woman, she believes that some opportunities may not have been offered because people assumed a woman would not fit those roles.

Susan also experienced workplace harassment from another female manager in a different area, for reasons she considered unnecessary. She stated: *“The only time I went through workplace harassment and back then we didn’t even have that term was not from a man, but from a woman. So, to say I had abusive bosses in terms of tone and things like that, I didn’t, but I had this case and it was woman to woman. And we didn’t even have that concept at the time... She was a manager, not in my area, but she had influence in the company. I think that today, if she reflected on her actions, she would think differently. But it was over something trivial, unnecessary.”* This harassment generated feelings of guilt, such as believing she had missed an opportunity because of something she might not have done. Combined with her understanding at the time, this experience even affected her subsequent role. From a sectoral perspective, Susan noted that working in IT support made her feel that her specialization could limit future opportunities. She also emphasized the constant need for extra effort to avoid thinking that missed opportunities resulted from her own shortcomings. She reported mild impostor syndrome with each new role, especially due to the need to learn many new things after leaving her comfort zone. In this context, she also mentioned the need to assert herself at certain moments, despite having a different leadership style.

Marissa: Finally, the fifth participant, Marissa, also experienced motherhood as a significant challenge. With motherhood, work opportunities became quite limited; she managed to maintain daily routines but did not advance into leadership roles, as she had to “give up” certain professional opportunities to maintain time with her daughter. As a result, she mentioned the guilt women feel when they have to be away from their children because of work. Marissa also faced gender prejudice in various situations. She believes that women of her generation were often raised to serve their husbands and families, and she experienced

sexism in moments when opportunities were not offered to her because she was a woman, as well as sexism from other women, including herself. As examples, she mentioned a situation in which a man questioned her decision to streamline and better manage a meeting; project communications that were mostly directed to male professors; people addressing a man present in meetings instead of her, even when she held the highest position; and a man attempting to lead a meeting despite holding a lower position. Throughout her career, she believes she witnessed many instances of prejudice that she did not immediately recognize, only realizing them over time.

In addition, Marissa perceived the need for extra effort to gain recognition and to earn “space” on a daily basis so that, over time, people would acknowledge her work. In her view, even when women are invited to take on leadership roles, they must prove why they were chosen; when it is a man, no one questions it. In this context, she also faced female rivalry. Finally, she mentioned that early in her career she was afraid to assert herself in certain situations, felt the need to restrain her expressions, and had to learn leadership through practice.

RQ3. How were these challenges overcome?

Megan: Megan adopts the perspective of not associating women with any notion of inferiority. She has never considered that being a woman would place her at a disadvantage, and because this belief is naturally internalized, she believes she acted more assertively when facing potential challenges. According to the participant: *“You won’t unconsciously think, ‘What I say won’t matter because I’m a woman.’ You have the capacity to discuss.”* Megan also believes that it is especially important for women to demonstrate to their children that, regardless of circumstances, if you are capable of doing something, you will be recognized for it. For her, her main strategy is something deeply internalized: *“If you do a better job, you will be better recognized,”* emphasizing the importance of self-confidence. In this sense, she believes her upbringing played a major role. From a very young age, she helped at her family’s snack bar and learned from her father that all tasks could be performed by anyone, without distinctions between men and women. This shaped her understanding of responsibility as something natural. As a result, she has always assumed responsibility in the situations she faced, learning from an early age to remain in control and to exercise decision-making power.

When she perceived behavioral changes in the team due to her presence and gender, Megan addressed the situation directly, stating that if the team changed its behavior because she was there, it would not function properly. She emphasized that everyone should behave as they normally would, accepting one another as they are. She commented: *“[...] I said, ‘Guys, let’s agree on something. I’m not an alien. I also swear. Everyone can speak the way they used to, because if I come in here and you start behaving differently, it’s not going to work... If we’re going to be part of the same team, I have to accept you as you are, and you have to accept me as I am. And we’re going to be ourselves.”* Even so, Megan acknowledges that in some situations she still adopts a more traditionally masculine posture in order to interact and exert influence.

Regarding personal challenges such as motherhood and the double workload, both mentioned in RQ2, Megan adopts the strategy of always having paid help for household tasks and maintaining a strong family support network. Finally, she highlighted physical endurance and emotional resilience as qualities she believes women tend to have more than men. As she stated: *"I think women have more resilience, you know? Physical resilience, really, to endure certain things, and sometimes leadership requires endurance... Women, from childhood, go through certain things more intensely. Women menstruate, women have PMS, and they have to learn to live with all of that. They develop greater resistance to life's hardships. We get less frustrated, we can endure more things. That gives us power too, if we know how to use it well... When we think about emotional resilience, there's both physical endurance and emotional resilience, the ability to go through things and overcome them."*

Grace: For Grace, having a support network and unconditional support was what enabled her to reach leadership positions. In her case, this support network included her mother, her husband, and her daughters, as illustrated by the following excerpt: *"I had unconditional support from my family and my husband. And sometimes there's pressure that feels overwhelming, and hearing that you're capable, that you're capable of anything, even if we don't know whether we really are, helps you take a deep breath and move forward... In addition to all the support from my mother and husband, my daughters supported me a lot too. They understood. And it was an exchange."* In this context, maintaining open conversations within the family, clearly separating work from home life, and not bringing professional burdens into the household were strategies Grace used to deal with motherhood and the double workload. To understand whether her daughters were affected by her routine, she monitored their behavior to identify any signs of insecurity. She also emphasized being at peace with herself and recognizing the balance that her support network provided. While her professional life was challenging, her private life offered the conditions needed to manage these demands. In terms of domestic tasks, Grace also sought external support, hiring help for household cleaning when she felt it was necessary. According to her, she consistently analyzed situations holistically and sought practical solutions.

From a technical standpoint, Grace sought dialogue and listened to the experiences of more senior professionals. She views communication as a central challenge and therefore always aimed to listen carefully and understand different perspectives. With a solid understanding of what she heard, she was able to guide her team and make informed decisions. As a result, she received feedback from other managers who were surprised by how much she seemed to know. Grace, however, does not believe she knows more than others; rather, she attributes this perception to being fully mentally present in meetings, with "full presence." She also emphasized her affinity for challenges, viewing them as opportunities for growth and overcoming fear. As she stated: *"The harder it is, the more I want it. Delivering something easy is, in my mind, more of the same. Delivering something difficult makes you surpass yourself. You grow through challenges. I've always had that as a kind of flag. I like stress, challenge, difficulty, because I think it brings a much greater return. And this has been true since early in my career, even before working in technology. It helps you not be afraid to see what others might view negatively as something positive."*

Finally, regarding the covert sexual harassment she experienced, largely due to the male-dominated environment, Grace emphasized the need to be more attentive in such

contexts and to maintain relationships with clear boundaries. According to her: *"It was, throughout my experience, not just in leadership, but as a woman an experience that taught me to be more attentive in male environments. We need to have relationships, but relationships with space, with boundaries, with respect."*

Lamarr: The third interviewee also relied on a support network to reconcile domestic activities with professional life, but she primarily sought external support by hiring domestic help and services such as transportation for her children to school. In the context of the double workload, Lamarr noted that even though she has the option to work from home, she often chooses to go to the office because she believes she concentrates better and is more productive there. As she explained: *"Nowadays I manage it quite well, you know? I feel balanced. And as I told you, I use these supports so I can keep my mind focused... I have the option to work from home, but I go to the office almost every day because I'm more focused and productive there."* Regarding professional challenges, she sought additional knowledge and external support to help her adapt to her new management role, and also sought medical support to better cope with the demands of leadership.

Susan: Susan relied on a support network and emphasized the importance of understanding, patience, and emotional support from those around her. Balancing personal and professional life helped her recognize that she has other priorities, which contributed to not positioning herself within an impostor syndrome mindset. As she stated: *"Today I realize that I don't let this focus on the company dominate everything. I understand that I have other priorities, and maybe that gave me more balance so I wouldn't put myself in an impostor syndrome position. Because I know there are other challenges beyond what we experience at work."* She also noted that she does not feel impostor syndrome because she allows herself to learn without underestimating anyone. According to Susan: *"I really allow myself to learn. I don't underestimate anyone... But every day I still think, my God, did I do everything? What's missing? Like now, I've been in this new position for a month, and sometimes I think I need to take more ownership of certain things to understand them better."* Additionally, she consistently sought dialogue, listening, and understanding, as she believes that people who live the reality are ultimately responsible for one's success or failure. She also observed others' management styles in order to identify what to do differently and how to improve.

Susan also reflected on the challenge of understanding why she often felt she did not receive leadership opportunities. Small achievements motivated her, while setbacks discouraged her. At specific moments, she sought psychological support, which helped her reinterpret past experiences and understand that in similar situations she would be better prepared. This allowed her to adapt and improve. As a result, she developed a more inward-looking approach, adjusting what she could control and achieving greater peace of mind. Ultimately, Susan recognized that facing these challenges helped her become a better person and understand that difficulties would pass or that sometimes it simply was not the right moment.

Regarding gender prejudice, Susan acknowledged that there is a different lens through which women are viewed in organizations. However, she believes that focusing on personal growth, rather than solely on organizational change, contributes to her own development. As she explained: *"Sometimes it's not subtle, but we feel there's competition or a different kind of look. And then it's up to us to notice the signs and see what we can do. Sometimes I don't*

even think about it for the company, I think about myself. Because this is something that stays with me; it's my baggage. I'm just building on it."

Marissa: Marissa does not tolerate any form of prejudice and actively responds to discriminatory remarks, which helps her deal with challenges such as prejudice in general. At the same time, she learned not to be overly self-critical in moments when she feels she could have acted differently or when she initially hesitated to assert herself due to her more assertive style. As she stated: *"There are situations where you have to hold back in the moment, and later you think, 'I should have answered, I should have spoken.' And you can't do it at that moment. I think it's a learning process. The most important thing is not blaming yourself or being too hard on yourself. That's very difficult. I've had moments in my life when I was much harder on myself for certain positions or attitudes. Nowadays, I don't criticize myself as much for that."* In addition, Marissa also has a support network, primarily external, including the ability to rely on a nanny and daycare to help with motherhood.

RQ4. In a leadership position, are these challenges the same?

Megan: Megan mentioned that the double workload remains a challenge that weighs heavily on women at work and, in her view, represents the greatest challenge. As a leader, regardless of being a man or a woman, she highlighted the need to balance team development while meeting all organizational demands and, consequently, keeping people engaged and believing in what they have set out to do. For Megan, *"the essence of leadership is to inspire."* She considers it a major responsibility to inspire those who work alongside her, because, in her view, a job title grants authority, but recognition comes from influence and guidance.

Grace: For Grace, the challenge of leadership is primarily technical. It involves delivering projects within budget and deadlines, as well as managing people from a technical perspective, such as coordinating projects with other managers and ensuring that managers are able to properly control teams and deliveries in order to achieve expected results. Finally, another challenge is identifying skilled professionals who fit the specific needs of roles within a project.

Lamarr: The third participant, Lamarr, although not explicitly identifying the double workload, indicates through her statements that it remains a present challenge. She explained that when personal matters arise, she allows herself time to address them and, once resolved, returns to her "professional mode" to listen to and motivate people. In this sense, dealing with people can also be quite challenging, as she believes that in order to influence others, leaders themselves need to be well. In a more recent situation, Lamarr mentioned that a woman on her team did not sympathize with her when she took over a project due to a previous negative experience with another female manager, which may be understood as a manifestation of gender prejudice among women themselves. Additionally, Lamarr commented on the need to recognize and assume that, at times, she herself may commit actions that could be considered politically incorrect, which leads her to self-monitor and remain attentive to such issues.

Susan: For Susan, the double workload continues to be a challenge, but currently a positive one. She also understands that management positions inherently involve challenges, as people expect leaders to somehow exceed expectations, creating high demands on leadership roles. Moreover, there is a constant need to demonstrate results to the organization. In her view, when everything is going well, things are considered acceptable, but any deviation within the team becomes a significant issue. As another example, after structuring the area for which she is responsible, Susan mentioned being strongly pressured regarding deliverables. Finally, she noted that because she always felt the need to make herself available, to her team and to external clients, an “overextended network” was formed, which negatively affected her time and limited what she allowed herself to do.

Marissa: The fifth participant stated that prejudice regarding women’s roles in society continues to affect her to this day. For example, the end of her marriage is often attributed to her constant dedication to work. In her view, men are perceived as “growing in life” when they are focused on work, even when they are older and single, often described as enjoying life. Women, however, are perceived as “unwanted” or lacking independence. As she explained: *“If a man is working, growing in life, people say, ‘Wow, he’s the guy.’ A 50-year-old single man, my age, for example, is seen as someone enjoying life. A woman, on the other hand, is seen as someone nobody wanted. That’s the way society sees it, unfortunately. And it’s still very, very present.”* During her time as vice provost in academia, it was common for decisions to be made without her involvement from the beginning; she was often informed only after everything had already been decided. For Marissa, women therefore continue to have to earn their place anew with each leadership position they assume.

RQ5. What motivated you to pursue a leadership position?

Megan: Megan mentioned that the recognition she received when she temporarily replaced her manager, combined with the fact that she enjoyed performing managerial duties and realized that others appreciated her work as well, helped her understand that this was the path she wanted to follow. She shared: *“I think it was at that moment that I was able to experience it and receive recognition that I did it well. And I liked doing it. Then I said, people are enjoying what I’m doing and I’m enjoying what I’m doing. So this is the path. This is where I need to invest.”* In addition, the opportunity to gain a broader understanding of the field reinforced her decision to pursue a career as an IT director.

Grace: For Grace, her initial motivation was financial. Over the course of her trajectory, she received opportunities as a consequence of her constant desire to learn more and expand her professional background, even though she was not initially aiming for leadership positions. As she stated: *“The challenges kept coming, I kept responding, and things kept happening. It was much more about learning and expanding my knowledge than about climbing positions. My curiosity was always much stronger than that.”*

Lamarr: Lamarr naturally identified more with people than with the technical work itself. She felt more fulfilled working with people than working directly with technology, understanding that recognizing and addressing the needs of team members is central to her way of

managing. She also mentioned the behavior of a former manager who positively surprised her with his leadership style and became a key source of inspiration, particularly because of his ability to lead the team and relate to people. Even while managing around 70 people and handling multiple responsibilities, he always made time for her when she sought guidance. As she recalled: *"I always say this: he would look at me and say, 'Of course. I have time for you. What do you need?' That was an impressive form of support. A simple phrase, in a simple moment, that inspired me— it inspired my career. I'll tell you, I always wanted to be like that manager I had."*

Susan: For Susan, people were the greatest motivation. In her view, getting to know and understanding people's experiences is extremely valuable. As she explained: *"People. Not just people, but when I say people it's because I really enjoy getting to know them and understanding their stories. It's very enriching what we receive in terms of information and experience, even in interviews. I'm always grateful for interviews, because you hear things you don't expect, whether positive or experiences from someone's life. And when someone allows themselves to share that, it's already very meaningful."* Beyond people, Susan also saw leadership as an opportunity to acquire more knowledge, which would enable her to reach new positions, meet different people, and experience new routines. Finally, she identified self-challenge as another motivating factor.

Marissa: Marissa identified two main motivations. The first is her belief that she could do things differently, or better, when something is not working as it should. When she observes situations that do not align with her expectations or values, she feels motivated to become involved in finding solutions. As she stated: *"What really motivates me is looking at something and thinking, I can do better than the person who's doing this, or I would do many things differently. I would say, 'No, this isn't right. I would do it differently.'" Her second motivation is the desire to increase women's participation. This motivation has even led her to accept responsibilities that she believes she should no longer need to take on in her current position. She expressed frustration when she noticed the absence of women in meetings, stating: "...every time I see a table with no women, it irritates me so much. I say, people, we are very far from achieving equality or anything close to that."*